

Supplementary Table 2. Assessment of the equality of variances.						
Medical feature	Survivors (n= 76)		Non-survivors (n= 35)		Assessment of the equality of variances	
	Shapiro-Wilk (W value)	Shapiro-Wilk (p value)	Shapiro-Wilk (W value)	Shapiro-Wilk (p value)	Analysis of variance (Lavene - F value)	Lavene (p value)
Age, years	0.961	0.02	0.958	0.203	1.692	0.213
Body weight	0.918	0.007	0.819	0.046	0.628	0.432
SpO2, %	0.61	<0.001	0.821	<0.001	4.239	0.0419
WBC, x10⁹/l	0.854	<0.001	0.84	<0.001	3.666	0.0581
Lymphocyte count, x10⁹/L	0.928	<0.001	0.855	<0.001	0.260	0.611
Monocyte count, x10⁹/L	0.96	0.22	0.819	<0.001	0.622	0.432
Neutrophil count, x10⁹/l	0.853	<0.001	0.812	<0.001	4.493	0.037
Eosinophil count, x10⁹/l	0.214	<0.001	0.535	<0.001	0.021	0.886
Basophil count, x10⁹/l	0.261	<0.001	0.881	0.003	1.373	0.244
RBC, x10¹²/l	0.923	<0.001	0.983	0.842	0.154	0.695
Haemoglobin, g/dL	0.981	0.3	0.977	0.672	2.736	0.101
Haematocrit, %	0.983	0.385	0.993	0.997	1.113	0.294
MCV, fL	0.812	<0.001	0.931	0.03	0.190	0.663
MCH, pg	0.913	<0.001	0.921	0.015	0.62	0.433
MCHC, g/dl	0.95	0.005	0.949	0.1	3.311	0.072
RDW-SD, fL	0.87	<0.001	0.945	0.111	4.072	0.046
Platelet count, x10⁹/l	0.967	0.043	0.942	0.624	0.111	0.739
C-reactive protein, mg/L	0.827	<0.001	0.89	0.002	1.043	0.309
Procalcitonin, ng/mL	0.162	<0.001	0.609	<0.001	1.560	0.215
Total bilirubin, mg/dL	0.342	<0.001	0.0214	<0.001	0.163	0.687
AST, U/L	0.431	<0.001	0.784	<0.001	2.076	0.153
ALT, U/L	0.748	<0.001	0.57	<0.001	1.066	0.304
ALP, U/L	0.497	<0.001	0.811	<0.001	0.752	0.388
GGT, U/L	0.452	<0.001	0.769	<0.001	0.006	0.937
LDH, U/L	0.71	<0.001	0.816	<0.001	0.925	0.339
Lactate, mmol/L	0.943	0.028	0.8	<0.001	2.963	0.09
Amylase, U/L	0.741	0.002	0.26	<0.001	1.867	0.287
Lipase, U/L	0.574	<0.001	0.342	<0.001	8.654	0.005
Creatinine, mg/dL	0.916	<0.001	0.651	<0.001	21.402	<0.001

BUN, mg/dL	0.835	<0.001	0.927	0.171	22.143	<0.001
Glucose, mg/dL	0.87	<0.001	0.731	<0.001	0.169	0.682
Fibrinogen, mg/dL	0.946	0.025	0.945	0.246	0.017	0.895
aPTT, s	0.925	<0.001	0.933	0.104	0.669	0.415
PT-INR	0.586	<0.001	0.869	0.002	0.181	0.671
PT, s	0.588	<0.001	0.887	0.004	0.206	0.651
D-dimer, ng/mL	0.535	<0.001	0.421	<0.001	13.969	<0.001
Sodium, mmol/L	0.88	<0.001	0.976	0.611	0.074	0.787
Potassium, mmol/L	0.99	0.691	0.927	0.022	0.49	0.485
Magnesium, mg/dL	0.14	<0.001	0.881	0.033	1.090	0.3
Calcium, mg/dL	0.967	0.155	0.935	0.123	0.732	0.395
Troponin, ng/L	0.77	<0.001	0.585	<0.001	9.349	0.003
Creatine kinase-MB, U/L	0.417	<0.001	0.946	0.311	4.373	0.041
CK, U/L	0.234	<0.001	0.483	<0.001	3.369	0.07
NT-proBNP, pg/mL	0.609	<0.001	0.658	<0.001	32.706	<0.001
Acidity-basicity	0.844	0.014	0.951	0.378	2.813	0.103
PaCO₂, mmHg	0.921	0.202	0.922	0.109	0.483	0.492
PaO₂, mmHg	0.98	0.97	0.965	0.652	1.038	0.316
HCO₃, mmol/L	0.917	0.174	0.908	0.058	0.542	0.467
Hemoglobin oxygen saturation, %	0.645	<0.001	0.772	<0.001	5.612	0.024
Base excess, mmol/L	0.82	0.007	0.923	0.113	5.493	0.025
Oxyhemoglobin, %	0.645	<0.001	0.777	<0.001	5.527	0.025
Deoxyhemoglobin, %	0.699	<0.001	0.771	<0.001	5.322	0.027
Opacity score	0.897	<0.001	0.899	0.029	2.776	0.01
Volume of opacity (ml)	0.749	<0.001	0.827	0.001	1.172	0.282
Percentage of opacity	0.762	<0.001	0.827	0.001	6.329	0.0145
Volume of high opacity (ml)	0.748	<0.001	0.844	0.003	12.876	0.001
Percentage of high opacity	0.73	<0.001	0.825	0.001	22.273	<0.001
Mean HU total	0.928	0.001	0.912	0.052	3.731	0.057
Mean HU of opacity	0.897	<0.001	0.951	0.324	0.99	0.322